

Interview Maurizion Longoni
Volandia
5.11.2021 / 2h

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Updated: 2021-07-28

WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys_ Guidelines for interviews.

- Presentation of the museum

Volandia is owned by private foundation, no public funding, they live on tickets. Attractivity of collections is very important to have visitors and have them back.

Foundation was created in 2005, in order to create a museum center dedicated to the world of aeronautics and its history, has set itself the following aims:

- protection, promotion and enhancement of things of artistic and historical interest with particular attention to aircraft, equipment, documentation and anything else belonging to the world of aeronautics;
- promotion of a model of local economic development with particular reference to the history, culture and industrial tradition of the province of Varese;
- promotion and realization of cultural and museum activities, organization of permanent and / or temporary exhibitions, institutions of archives and libraries, restoration laboratories with specific and non-exclusive regard to the history of local aeronautics.

The museum is located at Milano Malpensa airport. Very young museum, almost 100 flying machines.

Maurizion Longoni (ML) is Conservator of the museum, but works only 1 or 2 days per week
ML has a background as aerospace engineer ; he worked in aerospace industry for many years and then switched to industry

ML is also involved with an aeronautical association, which is located in museum as a 2nd workshop. This association will celebrate 30 years in 2022. It has already restored 26 aircrafts , some of which are in many places around the world.

This association doesn't work only for the Volandia museum but mainly and is located there. Members of the association have no formal training in conservation. Learning from experience, visit to many museums and restorations shops internationally (Imperial war museum).

Next year 30 years

Aeronautical restoration association 26 aircrafts in 30 years, some of which are in many places around the world. The association is still alive, is the 2nd workshop of the museum. Not only work for the museum, but mainly and located there.

No training in proper conservation

Visit to many museums and restorations shops international.

Association started when ML was working for Maki, to restore an Italian fighter fallen in Libya and brought back to Canada as war prize. This airplane is in USA Air Force museum in Dayton, Ohio.

Italy sold to Sweden 50 Italian aircrafts CA 42 ? Sira 42 ? ML has rebuilt one, approx. 80% in weight of « original material », but with parts from different countries. Arlequino result.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project ? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection ? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach ? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

Volandia are not the first ones called/involved in wrecks recovery, normally goes to Museo Storico dell'Aeronautica.

Volandia has good relationship with the airforce. They are currently involved in the restoration of a P44, just received in October 21. The aircraft is not a wreck that has been recovered, but it has been outside for many years and then in bad storage ; but overall not so bad condition, missing parts, light corrosion ; another experience.

ML has experience managing wrecks from previous occasions with the association. Then, not conservation, but restoration of 2 other planes according to « museum standards in the 70 & 80 ». The reference was a Book by Bob Markish, that states that people want to see airplane as it was in working conditions. The « good practice » from there was to conserve what is existing, replace what is not conservable that can be distinguishable, remake what is missing make it recognizable, but to make the aircraft complete. This was the bible at the time.

Case of B-51 : Volandia contacted from the beginning, planned from the beginning to get it at the museum. Rather complex situation. Wreck is property of the Italian Airforce, who must give authorisation. Ministry of Culture also has to be asked as wreck is more than 70 years old is under protection for historical artefacts. Ministry of Culture didn't know what to do. Also need for local authorizations.

This situation is quite usual situation for legal status.

Future projects around wrecks : Volandia is interested in working more with this kind of projects.

- Concept of “conservation” : Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle ? How do you define long term ? What does the idea of “conservation” mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Volandia was founded 12 years ago, still young museum.

Modern airplanes, ex military, that still flies : the airplane makes the final flight and ML takes the airplane to put it the museum directly. Several examples of that situation in Volandia.

For WWII airplanes : choice to be made by conservator. What we receive has to be kept as received ? or does an old airplane need to be made more understandable by public ?

Example 1 : T6 texan, training aircraft, very commonly produced. Received one that had been left in the open for many years. Some parts had been stolen (instruments, original engine), fabric was damaged, some pieces replaced. Approximately 80% of airplane was still there. The goal here was to fix this airplane at a moment of its life = last five years of its operational life. Search around on the

collection market for missing parts, replacement of fabric and right type of engine, anti-corrosion treatment (on outside parts before painted).

Treatment for metalparts : going to bare metal, then applying a strontium or chromium based primer + paint of modern type or older type (depending on future of airplane)

older paint : nitrocellulose paint

Modern type : 2 components paint, usually acrylic, more resistant for outdoors.

Carefull use of chromate based primers : more efficient and less expensive option for old aluminium alloys.

Example 2 : 5 years ago. Recovery of wreck or parts of B-51 Mustang from lake Garda. The aircraft had fallen into the water because of engine accident.

Team of sea divers found the wrecks, recovery was decided.

The wreck was in really bad condition, so there was no thinking of putting together an airplane.

Treatment of the different parts has been carried out separately and in different ways.

- Propeller : cleaned and covered with wax-based protection to avoid damage from humidity
- Engine : not lucky, very corroded, Mg parts disappeared, Fe parts very corroded except exhausts. 2 approaches : removal of surface dirt/dust/deposits. Pressure cleaning with water and brushes.
- Fe parts : protected by rust converter phosphate based, leave the rusty surface black
- Al parts : sanded to clean surface oxidation + surface protection with microcrystalline wax

Al on structural parts (wings, tail) . method from RAF = spray with citric acid ; mild, not pollutant, reusable. No time and facilities in Volandia to do the same. Used citric acid, but less diluted, less professional approach. Just sprayed several times, approximately twice a week, all inside and outside of parts. Even shorter time than RAF, for a couple of months. Good results on surface oxidation + corrosion products (considered as a mix, blue ones, white ones). Water rinse at the end of the 2 months.

Parts are not yet on display, still under cover, to check how they evolve in time. Mixed results : treatment did not stop corrosion, new corrosion is developing at a much slower rate (all type of corrosion)

Type of wrecks are used as a test.

No scientific approach, wanted to try more different types that have heard off.

(Dornier RAF = 1st german aircraft shot down in UK)

• Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

2 restoration teams and 2 workshops

1 team is unexperienced volunteers, do maintenance, interventions in the exhibits. Variable number depending on how many things to do 3/4 up to 7/8.

1 team is more professional : experienced former workers from aeronautic industry, have know-how and experience. 4 people, all volunteers. But no formal conservation training.

Separated work tasks, sometimes small help

Decisions made by ML, depends on type of interventions and the time available. Sometime important restoration but no deadline, done by less experienced people. On the contrary, smaller things need to be done more quickly so done by the more experienced.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

Volandia is located in the buildings of one of the first airplane factories, between 1915 and 1930, still in original condition, protected buildings. Not possible to modify structure of building. No thermal regulation in the building. Humidity doesn't vary much, is not main problem. Temperature has much more amplitude, – 10 to 38° C outside.

Majority of airplanes are kept indoors. Only the bigger ones are outside, 4 for now. All WWII aircrafts are inside.

Pollution : very close to Malpensa airport, airpath for taking off is on the side of the building. Not major concern at the moment for Volandia.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation ? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

Not observed consequences on WWII pieces, but museum is very young, 12 years is too young to see visible changes.

Volunteers have dusting maintenance 1/month indoors, 1/year cleaning on the ones outdoors.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections ?

Today ML and teams know more what needs to be done according to the current standards in conservation. They did not work so much on WWII airplanes since the B-51. More modern airplanes, which are approached a bit differently.

Principle of reversibility is very important : for replacement, addition of what is missing.

ML approach in practice has evolved somehow. Common sense used in the first years is not regretted. Maybe some regrets for the Dayton airplane, maybe

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant) ? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A) ?

Al issues in all types and periods of airplanes.

Series 7000 (7075), very much used in Italy in 70 and 80 : very prone to stress and laminate corrosion. Very related to humidity.

Less concern for the Al in WWII wrecks.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

Today, people in Italy are much more interested in WWII period, not so much the case 20-30 years ago.

Italy surrendered in Sept. 43. North under German domination, South with Allies and former King.
After the war, Italians were losers for 2nd time.
After war, aeronautical industry completely destroyed + Italy not allowed to build airplanes until 1947.
Civil airlines were using DC3. Italian airforce used British or American airplanes.
Wrecks from war reused or burnt if wood was present. No will to preserve the WWII heritage after war, as it was associated with bad memory. SIA 42 most widely built airplane in WWII, none of them was kept. Sold in parts in to other countries.

This situation is reflected in Italian airforce museums, very few airplanes from WWII.
End of war some Messerschmitt for North or P44 for South
Not so much interest for foreign aircrafts.

Expectations of the public coming to Volandia : mainly families, mainly driven by masculine members + 10% of adult enthusiasts about airplanes, Volandia believes that what needs to be shown is « real aircraft », that can be understood by the public and also as the result of huge effort for restoration and conservation. ML is not sure the public can understand that. Show airplanes as when they where alive. Volandia is also a theme park, which is a different approach then a museum. More for family fun and children.

People want to see the cockpit first : emphasis to make it as complete as possible (restoration, replacement).